

Properties of an Unbounded Solutions of a Fourth Order Neutral Dynamic Equations

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Abstract- In this paper, the author studied, the properties of an unbounded solutions of a class of fourth order dynamic equation of the form

$$\left(r(t) \left(x(t) + p(t)x(\alpha(t)) \right)^{\Delta^2} \right)^{\Delta^2} + g(t)G(x(\beta(t))) - h(t)H(x(\gamma(t))) = 0 \quad (H)$$

for $t \in [t_0, \infty)_{\mathbb{T}}$ where \mathbb{T} is a time scale with $\sup \mathbb{T} = +\infty$, $t_0 (\geq 0) \in \mathbb{T}$ are studied under the assumption

$$H_0 \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{t}{r(t)} \Delta t = \infty \text{ and } ((H_0)' \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{t}{r(t)} \Delta t < \infty \text{ for various ranges of } p(t).$$

Keywords- dynamic equation, delay, oscillation, positive and negative coefficients, bounded solution.

I. INTRODUCTION

In [3] and [4], Parhi and Tripathy have discussed the oscillatory and asymptotic properties of solutions of fourth order differential equation of the form

$$(r(t)(y(t) + p(t)y(t - \alpha)))'''' + q(t)G(y(t - \sigma)) = 0, \quad t \in [0, \infty)$$

where $r, q \in C([0, \infty), (0, \infty))$, $G \in C(R, R)$, $p \in C((0, \infty), R)$ and α, σ are positive real constants; are studied under the assumption

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{t}{r(t)} dt = \infty \text{ or } \int_0^{\infty} \frac{t}{r(t)} dt < \infty.$$

In [5] and [6], Panigrahi, Graef and Ramireddy have discussed the oscillatory and asymptotic properties of solutions of fourth order dynamic equation of the form

$$(r(t)(y(t) + p(t)y(\alpha(t)))^{\Delta^2})^{\Delta^2} + q(t)G(x(\beta(t))) - h(t)H(x(\gamma(t))) = 0$$

and

$$(r(t)(y(t) + p(t)y(\alpha(t)))^{\Delta^2})^{\Delta^2} + q(t)G(x(\beta(t))) - h(t)H(x(\gamma(t))) = f(t), \quad t \in [t_0, \infty)_{\mathbb{T}}, \text{ where } T \text{ is a timescale,}$$

$r, q \in C_{rd}([t_0, \infty), (0, \infty)), p, h, f \in C_{rd}([t_0, \infty), R), G, H \in C(R, R)$ and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in C_{rd}(T, T)$ are increasing functions such that $\alpha(t) \leq t, \beta(t) \leq t, \gamma(t) \leq t$ with $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \alpha(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \beta(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \gamma(t) = \infty$; are studied under the assumption $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{t}{r(t)} \Delta t = \infty$ or $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{\sigma(t)}{r(t)} \Delta t < \infty$.

When we are concerned with oscillation of all solutions of the following equation

$$(p(t)(u(t) + r(t)u(\alpha(t)))^{\Delta^2})^{\Delta^2} + g(t)G(u(\beta(t))) = 0$$

in [7] and [8] by Tripathy under two sorts of assumptions

$$\int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{t}{p(t)} \Delta t = \infty \quad \text{or} \quad \int_{t_0}^{\infty} \frac{t}{p(t)} \Delta t < \infty.$$

Similarly, in an another work [9] of Grace and Zafer, we can find all solutions of oscillatory problem for the dynamic equations

$$(p(t)((u(t) + r(t)u(\alpha(t)))^{\Delta^3})^{\mu_1})^{\Delta} + g(t)u^{\mu_2}(\beta(t)) = 0$$

under the following restrictions:

(i) μ_1 and μ_2 are the quotient of odd positive integers such that $\mu_2 \leq \mu_1$,

(ii) $|r(t)| \leq 1$

and (iii) $\int_{t_0}^{\infty} p^{-\frac{1}{\mu_1}}(t) \Delta t = \infty, t_0 > 0$.

A time scale is an arbitrary nonempty closed subset of real number. We denote a timescale by T , the forward jump operator σ is defined as $\sigma(t) = \inf\{s \in T : s > t\}$, the delta derivative of f is denoted by f^{Δ} , the useful double integration formulas are

$$\int_v^u \int_v^t f(\theta) \Delta \theta \Delta s = \int_v^u (u - \sigma(t)) f(t) \Delta t$$

and

$$\int_v^u \int_t^u f(\theta) \Delta \theta \Delta s = \int_v^u (\sigma(t) - v) f(t) \Delta t.$$

For more basics in time scale refer the books [1, 2]. In this work, we assume the following assumptions on G, α and β .

(H₁) $G(xy) \geq G(x)G(y)$ for $x, y \in R$ and $x, y > 0$;

(H₂) $G(-x) = -G(x)$ for $x \in R$;

(H₃) there exists $\lambda > 0$ such that $G(x) + G(y) \geq \lambda G(x + y)$ for $x, y \in R$ and $x, y > 0$;

(H₄) $\alpha(\beta(t)) = \beta(\alpha(t))$ for all $t \in [t_0, \infty)_T$.

Remark 1. The prototype of G satisfying (H₁), (H₂) and (H₃) could be of the form

$$G(u) = (a^* + b^*|u|^{\gamma})|u| \operatorname{sgn} u \quad \text{And} \quad G(u) = |u|^{\eta} \operatorname{sgn} u$$

where $a^* \geq 1, b^* \geq 1, \gamma \geq 0$ and $\eta > 0$.

Let $t_{-1} = \inf_{t \in [t_0, \infty)_T} \{\alpha(t), \beta(t), \gamma(t)\}$. By a solution of (H), we mean a function $x \in C_{rd}([t_{-1}, \infty)_T, \mathbb{R})$ such

that $x(t) + p(t)x(\alpha(t)) \in C_{rd}^2([t_0, \infty)_T, R), r(t)(x(t) + p(t)x(\alpha(t)))^{\Delta^2} \in C_{rd}^2([t_0, \infty)_T, R)$ and satisfies (H) identically on $[t_0, \infty)_T$.

. A solution of (H) is said to be oscillatory if there exists a sequence $\{s_n\}$ in $[t_0, \infty)_T$ such that $(s_n)x(\sigma(s_n)) \leq 0$; Otherwise, it is called non oscillatory.

II. SOME PREPARATORY RESULTS

In this section, we present some preparatory results which are useful for our discussion. Throughout our text, we use the quasi-derivative operators on D as follows.

$$D_0 u = u, D_1 u = D_0 u^{\Delta}, D_2 u = r D_1^{\Delta} u, D_3 u = D_2^{\Delta} u, \text{ and } D_4 u = D_3^{\Delta} u.$$

Lemma 2.1. Let (H₀) hold and u be a real valued function on $[t_0, \infty)_T$ such that $D_4 u(t) \leq 0$ for large t . If $u(t) > 0$ ultimately, then one of the Cases (a) and (b) holds for large t and if $u(t) < 0$ ultimately, then one of the Cases (b), (c), (d) and (e) holds for large t , where

- (a) $D_1u(t) > 0$, $D_2u(t) > 0$ and $D_3u(t) > 0$,
- (b) $D_1u(t) > 0$, $D_2u(t) < 0$ and $D_3u(t) > 0$,
- (c) $D_1u(t) < 0$, $D_2u(t) < 0$ and $D_3u(t) > 0$,
- (d) $D_1u(t) < 0$, $D_2u(t) < 0$ and $D_3u(t) < 0$,
- (e) $D_1u(t) < 0$, $D_2u(t) > 0$ and $D_3u(t) > 0$,

Lemma 2.2. Let (H_0') hold and u be a real valued function on $[t_0, \infty)_{\mathbb{T}}$ such that $D_4u(t) \leq 0$ for large t . If $u(t) > 0$ ultimately, then one of the Cases (a) - (d) holds for large t and if $u(t) < 0$ ultimately, then one of the Cases (b) - (f) holds for large t , where

- (a) $D_1u(t) > 0$, $D_2u(t) > 0$ and $D_3u(t) > 0$,
- (b) $D_1u(t) > 0$, $D_2u(t) < 0$ and $D_3u(t) > 0$,
- (c) $D_1u(t) > 0$, $D_2u(t) < 0$ and $D_3u(t) < 0$,
- (d) $D_1u(t) < 0$, $D_2u(t) > 0$ and $D_3u(t) > 0$,
- (e) $D_1u(t) < 0$, $D_2u(t) < 0$ and $D_3u(t) > 0$,
- (f) $D_1u(t) < 0$, $D_2u(t) < 0$ and $D_3u(t) < 0$.

III. UNBOUNDED OSCILLATION RESULTS

In this section, unbounded oscillation criteria for (H) are established under the assumptions (H_0) and (H_0') . Before stating our main results, we assume the following hypothesis for our use in the sequel :

$$B[u, v] = \int_v^u \frac{(u-\sigma(t))(t-v)}{r(t)} \Delta t, u > t > v;$$

$$C[u, v] = \int_v^u \frac{(\sigma(t)-v)(u-t)}{r(t)} \Delta t, u > t > v;$$

and $D[u, v] = \int_v^u \frac{(\sigma(t)-v)(t-v)}{r(t)} \Delta t, u > t > v;$

Theorem 3.1. Let $0 \leq p(t) \leq p < \infty$ and $\beta(t) \leq \alpha(\alpha(t))$, $\gamma^{-1}(t) \leq \beta(t)$. Suppose that, (H_0') and $(H_1) - (H_4)$ hold. If

- (H₅) $\int_T^\infty \frac{\sigma(s)}{r(s)} \int_s^\infty \sigma(t)h(t)\Delta t \Delta s < \infty;$
- (H₆) $\frac{G(u)}{u} \geq M_1 > 0$ for $u \neq 0;$
- (H₇) $\limsup_{s \rightarrow \infty} \int_s^{\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))} Q(t)G[B(\beta(t), \beta(s))] \Delta t > \frac{1+G(a)}{\lambda M_1};$
- (H₈) $\limsup_{s \rightarrow \infty} \int_s^{\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))} Q(t)G[C(\beta(t), \beta(s))] \Delta t > \frac{1+G(a)}{\lambda M_1};$
- (H₉) $\limsup_{s \rightarrow \infty} \int_s^{\gamma^{-1}(s)} Q(t)G[D(\gamma^{-1}(t), \gamma^{-1}(s))] \Delta t > \frac{1+G(a)}{\lambda M_1};$
- (H₁₀) $\limsup_{s \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\beta(s)}^s Q(t)G[D(\beta(s), \beta(t))] \Delta t > \frac{1+G(a)}{\lambda M_1};$

hold, where $Q(t) = \min\{g(t), g(\alpha(t))\}$ for $t \geq t_{-1}$, then every unbounded solution of (H) oscillates.

Proof: Assume the contrary that, $x(t)$ be an unbounded non-oscillatory solution of (H) such that $x(t) > 0$ for $t \geq t_0$. Then there exists $t_1 \in [t_0, \infty)_{\mathbb{T}}$ such that $x(t)$, $x(\alpha(t))$, $x(\beta(t))$ and $x(\gamma(t))$ are all positive for $t \geq t_1$. Setting

$$y(t) = x(t) + p(t)x(\alpha(t)) \tag{3.1}$$

$$k(t) = \int_t^\infty \frac{(\sigma(s)-t)}{r(s)} \int_s^\infty (\sigma(\theta) - s)h(\theta)H(x(\gamma(\theta)))\Delta \theta \Delta s \tag{3.2}$$

$$z(t) = y(t) - k(t) = x(t) + p(t)x(\alpha(t)) - k(t) \tag{3.3}$$

$$D_4z(t) = -g(t)G(x(\beta(t))) \leq 0 \tag{3.4}$$

for all $t \geq t_1$. Then there exists $t_2 \in [t_1, \infty)_{\mathbb{T}}$ such that $D_i z(t), i = 0,1,2,3$ are eventually of one sign on $[t_2, \infty)_{\mathbb{T}}$. Assume that, $z(t) > 0$. In what follows, we consider the Cases (a) - (d) of Lemma 2.2. Let Case (a) holds. For $u > s > v > t_2$,

$$D_2z(u) - D_2z(v) = \int_v^u D_3z(s)\Delta s \geq (u - v)D_3z(u),$$

implies

$$D_2z(u) \geq (u - v)D_3z(u)$$

or

$$r(u)D_1^\Delta z(u) \geq (u - v)D_3z(u)$$

Or

$$D_1^\Delta z(u) \geq \frac{(u - v)}{r(u)} D_3z(u)$$

For $u > \theta > v > t_2$, we have

$$D_1z(u) - D_1z(v) = \int_v^u \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)} D_3z(\theta)\Delta s,$$

Implies

$$D_1z(u) \geq D_3z(u) \int_v^u \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)} \Delta \theta,$$

For $u > t > v > t_2$, we have

$$z(u) - z(v) \geq \int_v^u D_3z(t) \int_v^t \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)} \Delta \theta \Delta t,$$

Or

$$z(u) \geq D_3z(u) \int_v^u \int_v^s \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)} \Delta \theta \Delta s$$

Or

$$z(u) \geq D_3z(u) \int_v^u \frac{(u - \sigma(t))(t - v)}{r(t)} \Delta s$$

Or

$$z(u) \geq D_3z(u)B[u, v] \tag{3.5}$$

From (3.4) and for $\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s)) > t > s > t_2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= D_4z(t) + g(t)G(x(\beta(t))) + G(p) \left[D_4z(\alpha(t)) + g(\alpha(t))G(x(\beta(\alpha(t)))) \right] \\ &\geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + Q(t) [G(x(\beta(t))) + G(p)G(x(\beta(\alpha(t))))] \\ &\geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + Q(t)[G(x(\beta(t))) + G(p(t))G(x(\alpha(\beta(t))))] \\ &\geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + Q(t)[G(x(\beta(t))) + G(p(t))G(x(\alpha(\beta(t))))] \\ &\geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + Q(t)\lambda[G(x(\beta(t)) + p(t)x(\alpha(\beta(t))))] \\ &\geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + \lambda Q(t)G(y(\beta(t))) \\ &\geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + \lambda Q(t)G(z(\beta(t))) \\ &\geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + \lambda Q(t)G[D_3z(\beta(t))]G(B[\beta(t), \beta(s)]) \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

Integrating the above inequality, from s to $\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))$, we obtain

$$\lambda \int_s^{\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))} Q(t)G(D_3z(\beta(t))B[\beta(t), \beta(s)])\Delta t \leq D_3z(s) + G(p)D_3z(\alpha(s))$$

implies

$$\lambda G(D_3z(\alpha(s))) \int_s^{\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))} Q(t)G[B[\beta(t), \beta(s)]]\Delta t \leq D_3z(\alpha(s)) + G(p)D_3z(\alpha(s)) \leq (1 + G(p))D_3z(\alpha(s))$$

Or

$$\int_s^{\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))} Q(t)G(B[\beta(t), \beta(s)])\Delta t \leq \frac{(1+G(p))D_3z(\alpha(s))}{\lambda G[D_3z(\alpha(s))]} \leq \frac{(1+G(p))}{\lambda M_1},$$

where $\beta(s) \leq \alpha(s)$.

Case (b). For $u > s > v > t_2$,

$$D_2z(u) - D_2z(v) = \int_v^u D_3z(s)\Delta s \geq (u - v)D_3z(u),$$

implies

$$-D_2z(v) \geq (u - v)D_3z(u)$$

Or

$$-r(v)D_1^\Delta z(v) \geq (u - v)D_3z(u)$$

Or

$$-D_1^\Delta z(v) \geq \frac{(u - v)}{r(v)} D_3z(u)$$

For $u > \theta > v > t_2$, we have

$$-D_1z(u) + D_1z(v) = \int_v^u \frac{(u - \theta)}{r(\theta)} D_3z(u)\Delta s,$$

implies

$$D_1z(v) \geq D_3z(u) \int_v^u \frac{(u - \theta)}{r(\theta)} \Delta \theta,$$

For $u > t > v > t_2$, we have

$$z(u) - z(v) \geq \int_v^u D_3z(u) \int_t^u \frac{(u - \theta)}{r(\theta)} \Delta \theta \Delta t,$$

Or

$$z(u) \geq D_3z(u) \int_v^u \int_t^u \frac{(u - \theta)}{r(\theta)} \Delta \theta \Delta t$$

Or

$$z(u) \geq D_3z(u) \int_v^u \frac{(\sigma(t) - v)(u - t)}{r(t)} \Delta t$$

Or

$$z(u) \geq D_3z(u)C[u, v] \tag{3.7}$$

As in Case (a), we have

$$0 \geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + \lambda Q(t)G(D_3z(\beta(t)))G(C[\beta(t), \beta(s)])$$

Integrating the above inequality, from s to $\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))$, we obtain

$$\int_s^{\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))} \lambda Q(t)G(D_3z(\beta(t)))G(C[\beta(t), \beta(s)])\Delta t \leq D_3z(s) + G(p)D_3z(\alpha(s))$$

Implies

$$\lambda G(D_3z(\alpha(s))) \int_s^{\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))} Q(t)G(C[\beta(t), \beta(s)])\Delta t \leq (1 + G(p))D_3z(\alpha(s)) \leq (1 + G(p))D_3z(\alpha(s))$$

Or

$$\int_s^{\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))} Q(t)G(C[\beta(t), \beta(s)])\Delta t \leq \frac{(1 + G(p))D_3z(\alpha(s))}{G(D_3z(\alpha(s)))} \leq \frac{(1 + G(p))}{\lambda M_1}$$

Case (c). For $u > s > v > t_2$,

$$D_2z(u) - D_2z(v) = \int_v^u D_3z(s)\Delta s \leq (u - v)D_3z(v)$$

implies

$$D_2z(u) \leq (u - v)D_3z(v)$$

or

$$r(u)D_1^\Delta z(u) \leq (u - v)D_3z(v)$$

or

$$-D_1^\Delta z(u) \geq -\frac{(u - v)}{r(u)}D_3z(v)$$

For $u > \theta > v > t_2$, we have

$$-D_1z(u) + D_1z(v) = \int_v^u \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)}(-D_3z(v))\Delta s,$$

implies

$$D_1z(v) \geq (-D_3z(v)) \int_v^u \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)}\Delta \theta,$$

For $u > s > v > t_2$, we have

$$z(u) - z(v) \geq \int_v^u (-D_3z(s)) \int_s^u \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)}\Delta \theta \Delta s,$$

Or

$$z(u) \geq (-D_3z(v)) \int_v^u \int_s^u \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)}\Delta \theta \Delta s$$

Or

$$z(u) \geq (-D_3z(v)) \int_v^u \frac{(\sigma(t) - v)(t - v)}{r(t)}\Delta t$$

Or

$$z(u) \geq (-D_3z(v))D[u, v] \tag{3.8}$$

As in Case (a), we have

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + \lambda Q(t)G(z(\beta(t))) \\ &\geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + \lambda Q(t)G(z(\gamma^{-1}(t))) \\ &\geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + \lambda Q(t)G((-D_3z(\gamma^{-1}(s))))G(D[\gamma^{-1}(t), \gamma^{-1}(s)]) \end{aligned}$$

Integrating the above inequality from s to $\gamma^{-1}(s)$, we obtain

$$\int_s^{\gamma^{-1}(s)} \lambda Q(t)G(-D_3z(\gamma^{-1}(s)))G(D[\gamma^{-1}(t), \gamma^{-1}(s)])\Delta t \leq -D_3z(\gamma^{-1}(s)) - G(p)D_3z(\gamma^{-1}(s))$$

implies

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda G(-D_3z(\gamma^{-1}(s))) \int_s^{\gamma^{-1}(s)} Q(t)G(D[\gamma^{-1}(t), \gamma^{-1}(s)])\Delta t &\leq (1 + G(p))(-D_3z(\gamma^{-1}(s))) \\ &\leq (1 + G(p))(-D_3z(\gamma^{-1}(s))) \end{aligned}$$

Or

$$\int_s^{\gamma^{-1}(s)} Q(t)G(D[\gamma^{-1}(t), \gamma^{-1}(s)])\Delta t \leq \frac{(1 + G(p))(-D_3z(\gamma^{-1}(s)))}{G(-D_3z(\gamma^{-1}(s)))} \leq \frac{(1 + G(p))}{\lambda M_1}$$

Case (d). For $u > s > v > t_2$,

$$D_2z(u) - D_2z(v) = \int_v^u D_3z(s)\Delta s \geq (u - v)D_3z(u)$$

implies

$$D_2z(u) \geq (u - v)D_3z(u)$$

or

$$r(u)D_1^\Delta z(u) \geq (u - v)D_3z(u)$$

Or

$$D_1^\Delta z(u) \geq \frac{(u - v)}{r(u)} D_3z(u)$$

For $u > \theta > v > t_2$, we have

$$D_1z(u) - D_1z(v) = \int_v^u \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)} (D_3z(\theta))\Delta\theta,$$

Implies

$$-D_1z(v) \geq D_3z(u) \int_v^u \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)} \Delta\theta,$$

For $u > t > v > t_2$, we have

$$z(v) \geq \int_v^u (D_3z(u)) \int_t^u \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)} \Delta\theta \Delta s,$$

Or

$$z(v) \geq D_3z(u) \int_v^u \int_t^u \frac{(\theta - v)}{r(\theta)} \Delta\theta \Delta s$$

Or

$$z(v) \geq D_3z(u) \int_v^u \frac{(\sigma(t) - v)(t - v)}{r(t)} \Delta t$$

Or

$$z(v) \geq D_3z(u)D[u, v] \tag{3.9}$$

As in Case (a), we have

$$0 \geq D_4z(t) + G(p)D_4z(\alpha(t)) + \lambda Q(t)G(D_3z(\beta(s)))G(D[\beta(s), \beta(t)])$$

Integrating the above inequality from $\beta(s)$ to s , we obtain

$$G(D_3z(\beta(s))) \int_{\beta(s)}^s Q(t)G(D[\beta(s), \beta(t)])\Delta t \leq D_3z(\beta(s)) + G(p)D_3z(\alpha(\beta(s)))$$

implies

$$\lambda G(D_3z(\beta(s))) \int_{\beta(s)}^s Q(t)G(D[\beta(s), \beta(t)])\Delta t \leq (1 + G(p))(D_3z(\beta(s)))$$

Or

$$\int_{\beta(s)}^s Q(t)G(D[\beta(s), \beta(t)])\Delta t \leq \frac{(1 + G(p))D_3z(\beta(s))}{G(D_3z(\beta(s)))} \leq \frac{(1 + G(p))}{\lambda M_1}$$

If $z(t) < 0$ for $t \geq t_2$, then $z(t) = y(t) - k(t) < 0$. From this, $x(t) \leq y(t) = x(t) + p(t)x(\alpha(t)) < k(t)$. Since $k(t) > 0$ and $k^\Delta(t) < 0$, so $k(t)$ is bounded, it follows that, $x(t)$ is bounded. Which is a contradiction to that, $x(t)$ is unbounded. This completes the proof of the theorem.

Theorem 3.2. Let $-1 < p(t) \leq 0$ for $t \in [t_0, \infty)_T$ and $\beta(t) \leq \alpha(t)$, $\gamma^{-1}(t) \leq \beta(t)$. Assume that, (H_0') , (H_1) , (H_2) , (H_5) and (H_6) hold. Furthermore, assume that

$$(H_{11}) \limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_s^{\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))} g(t)G[B(\beta(t), \beta(s))] \Delta t > \frac{1}{M_1};$$

$$(H_{12}) \limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_s^{\beta^{-1}(\alpha(s))} g(t)G[C(\beta(t), \beta(s))] \Delta t > \frac{1}{M_1};$$

$$(H_{13}) \limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_s^{\gamma^{-1}(s)} g(t)G[D(\gamma^{-1}(t), \gamma^{-1}(s))] \Delta t > \frac{1}{M_1};$$

$$(H_{14}) \limsup_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\beta(s)}^s g(t)G[D(\beta(s), \beta(t))] \Delta t > \frac{1}{M_1}$$

$$\text{and } (H_{15}) \alpha^n(t) = \alpha(\alpha^{n-1}(t)), \lim_{n \rightarrow t} \alpha^n(t) = \infty$$

hold. Then every unbounded solution of (H) oscillates.

Proof: Suppose on the contrary that, $x(t)$ be an unbounded nonoscillatory solution of (H) such that $x(t) > 0$, $x(\alpha(t)) > 0$, $x(\beta(t)) > 0$, $x(\gamma(t)) > 0$ for all $t \geq t_1 > t_0$. The case $x(t) < 0$ can similarly be dealt with due to (H_2) . Proceeding as in Theorem 3.1, we get (3.4). Then there exists a $t_2 > t_1$ such that $D_i x(t)$ for $i = 0, 1, 2, 3$ are eventually of one sign on $[t_2, \infty)_T$. Assume that, $z(t) > 0$ for $t \geq t_2$. Then $z(t) \leq x(t)$ for $t \geq t_2$ and hence (3.4) can be written as

$$D_4 z(t) + g(t)G(z(\beta(t))) \leq 0, t \geq t_2.$$

Ultimately, any one of four Cases (a) – (d) of Lemma 2.2 holds for $t \geq t_2$. We can apply the arguments of the cases of Theorem 3.1, to get contradictions to $(H_{11}) - (H_{14})$. Therefore, $z(t) < 0$ for $t \geq t_2$ and also $y(t) < k(t)$ for $t \geq t_2$ implies that $y(t)$ is bounded and hence $x(t)$ is bounded for $t \geq t_2$. Since $z(t)$ is monotonic, then $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} z(t)$ exists. On the otherhand, $x(t)$ is unbounded and therefore, it suggests that either $x(t) > x(\alpha(t))$ or $x(t) < x(\alpha(t))$ for $t \geq t_2$. If the former holds, then $z(t) = x(t) + p(t)x(\alpha(t)) - k(t) > (1 + p(t))x(\alpha(t)) - k(t) \rightarrow \infty$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$ gives a contradiction. If the later holds, then

$$x(t) < x(\alpha(t)) < x(\alpha^2(t)) < \dots < x(\alpha^n(t)) < \dots,$$

leads to the fact that $x(t)$ is bounded, which is absurd. Hence, the theorem is proved.

Theorem 3.3. Let $-\infty < p(t) < -1$ for $t \in [t_0, \infty)_T$. Assume that all conditions of Theorem 3.2 hold. If

$$(H_{16}) \int_0^\infty g(u)du = \infty$$

Then every unbounded solution of (H) oscillates.

Proof: On the contrary, we proceed as in the proof of Theorem 3.2, and the case $z(t) > 0$ is similar. When $z(t) < 0$ for $t \geq t_2$, we have that, $y(t) < k(t)$ for $t \geq t_2$, so $y(t)$ is bounded and follows that, $z(t)$ is bounded. Because, $z(t)$ is monotonic, $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} z(t)$ exists. Here, we consider Cases (b) – (f) of Lemma 2.2. For the Cases (b), (d), (e); since $x(t)$ is unbounded, then either $x(t) > x(\alpha(t))$ or $x(t) < x(\alpha(t))$ for $t \geq t_2$. Suppose that, $x(t) < x(\alpha(t))$ for $t \geq t_2$. Then $z(t) = x(t) + p(t)x(\alpha(t)) - k(t) < (1 + p(t))x(\alpha(t)) - k(t) \rightarrow -\infty$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$, which gives a contradiction to the existence of the limit. Hence,

$$x(t) > x(\alpha(t)) > x(\alpha^2(t)) > \dots > x(\alpha^n(t)) > \dots,$$

that is, $\liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} x(t) > 0$. Then there exists a $t_3 > t_2$ and $\eta > 0$ such that $x(\beta(t)) > \eta$ for $t \geq t_3$. Integrating (3.4) from t_3 to ∞ , we get a contradiction to (H_{16}) . In Cases (c) and (f), it is immediate to see that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} D_1 z(t) = -\infty$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} z(t) = -\infty$, so these cases are not possible. Hence, the proof of the theorem is complete.

Theorem 3.4. Assume that $0 \leq p(t) \leq p < \infty$ for $t \in [t_0, \infty)_T$. If (H_0) and $(H_1) - (H_8)$ hold, then every unbounded solution of (H) oscillates.

Proof: The proof of the theorem follows from Lemma 2.1 and Theorem 3.1. Hence, the details are omitted.

Theorem 3.5. Let $-1 < p(t) \leq 0$ for $t \in [t_0, \infty)_T$. If (H_0) , (H_1) , (H_2) , (H_5) , (H_6) , (H_{11}) and (H_{12}) hold, then every unbounded solution of (H) oscillates.

Proof. The proof of the theorem follows from Lemma 2.1 and Theorem 3.2 and hence the details are omitted.

Theorem 3.6. Let $-\infty < p(t) < -1$ for $t \in [t_0, \infty)_T$. If all the conditions of Theorem 5 hold and (H_{16}) hold, then every unbounded solution of (H) oscillates.

Proof: The proof of the theorem follows from Theorem 5 and Theorem 3 and hence the details are omitted.

Remark 3.7. It would be interesting to apply the results of this work to the following nonlinear dynamic equations

$$(r(t)(x(t) + p(t)x(\alpha(t)))^{\Delta^2})^{\Delta^2} + \sum_{i=1}^n (-1)^{i+1} g_i(t)G_i(x(\beta_i(t))) = f(t),$$

for the cases

$$, f(t) = 0 \text{ for all } t \in [t_0, \infty)_T \text{ or } f(t) \neq 0 \text{ for } t \in [t_0, \infty)_T.$$

Example 1. Consider, $T = R$,

$$(e^{-t}(x(t) + (-\frac{1}{25}e^\pi)x(t-\pi)))'''' + e^{\frac{3\pi}{2}} \left(\frac{52}{25}e^{-t} - e^{-3t} \right) x\left(t - \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) - e^{\frac{\pi}{2}}(e^{-2t} + e^{-\pi} \cos^2 t) e^{-t} \frac{x\left(t - \frac{\pi}{2}\right)}{1+x^2\left(t - \frac{\pi}{2}\right)} = 0, t \in \left[\frac{3\pi}{2}, \infty\right). \quad (3.10)$$

Equations (3.10), satisfies all the conditions of Theorem 5. Hence, every unbounded solution of (3.10) is oscillatory. In particular, $x(t) = e^t \sin t$ is an unbounded oscillatory solution of (3.10).

Example 2. Consider, $T = Z$,

$$\Delta^2 \left(e^n \Delta^2 (x(n) + (-1)x(n-2)) \right) + \{e(e+1)^2(e^2+1)^2 e^n + 4e(e^{-1}+1)^2 e^{-n} - \frac{e}{(n+1)e^{4n}}\} x(n-1) - e^2 \left(\frac{e^4 + e^{2n}}{(n+1)e^{4n}} \right) \frac{x(n-2)}{1+x^2(n-2)} = 0, n \geq 3. \quad (3.11)$$

Equations (3.11), satisfies all the conditions of Theorem 2. Hence, every unbounded solution of (3.11) is oscillatory. In particular, $x(n) = e^n \sin n$ is an unbounded oscillatory solution of (3.11).

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